

MODELING AND PREDICTION OF FRACTURE PROPERTIES IN NANO-GRAPHENE REINFORCED POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

In order to better understand the local influence of nanoparticle on the mechanical properties of the polymer, nanoscale analysis is necessary. In that context, this paper is directed towards understanding damage initiation and failure progression in advanced nanostructured composite materials using molecular dynamics. The critical value of the J-integral (J_{IC}) at crack initiation is related to the fracture toughness of the material, where the subscript I denotes the fracture mode (I=1, 2, 3). Therefore, the J-integral could be used as a suitable metric for estimating the crack driving force as well as the fracture toughness of the material as the crack begins to initiate. Further, the conventional isothermal definition of J-integral does not take into account the entropic contribution to the free energy, and consequently, may lead to significant over-estimation of the J-integral at the atomistic level, especially at finite temperatures. As a case study, the feasibility of computing the dynamic atomistic J-integral over the molecular dynamics (MD) domain at finite temperature is evaluated for a graphene nanoplatelet and the values are compared with results from linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) for isothermal crack initiation at 0 K and at 300 K. Atomistic J-integral computations are also performed using ReaxFF force field in order to simulate bond breakage during crack propagation. Good agreement is observed between the atomistic J and the LEFM results at 0 K, with predictable discrepancies at 300 K due to entropic effects. A novel cohesive-contour based methodology for computing J-integral is discussed and successfully applied to a graphene nanoplatelet. In order to account for the high strain-rates encountered in MD simulations, scaling laws will be developed to correlate fracture toughness predicted by the MD simulations to the toughness data obtained from compact tension fracture experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent literature suggests that significant improvements in the fracture toughness of a polymer and polymer composite are feasible with the inclusion of a few weight percent of nanoparticles in the polymer [1-4]. There is a diverse range of nanofillers used to enhance the properties of epoxy based nanocomposites [5-7]. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), owing to their exceptional mechanical properties, have been widely used as reinforcement in nanocomposites [9, 10]. Graphene, a single layer of graphite has garnered the attention of the scientific community in recent years and has an advantage of being cheaper than CNTs. It is a monolayer of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in a two dimensional lattice [11]. It is considered one of the strongest materials ever discovered in terms of

tensile strength [12], when considered in a defect free form, along with excellent thermal and electrical properties. Even a low weight percentage of graphene has been shown to significantly improve the properties of epoxy [13, 14] when a proper dispersion is obtained. There is also evidence of graphene being used for enhancing fracture properties of epoxy [15, 16]. Compact-tension (CT) fracture tests conducted as a part of this work corroborate these observations, as presented in Figure 1, showing an increase in peak failure load by 17% and a corresponding increase in fracture toughness by 35% over baseline specimens at room temperature for EPON-862 epoxy modified with 3 wt% nanographene. Further, in Figure 1, the transition from catastrophic brittle fracture for the baseline epoxy specimens to a more benign “stick-slip” type crack propagation for the nanographene-modified specimens implies significant crack blunting/bridging by the nanographene platelets leading to increased energy absorption and resistance to crack growth.

Figure 1. Compact tension fracture test results for baseline and nanographene reinforced EPON 862 epoxy specimens (at room temperature)

The fundamental mechanism for enhanced fracture toughness at the nanoscale is still not well understood. In order to better understand the local influence of nanoparticle on the mechanical properties of the composite, nanoscale analysis is necessary, which is the focus of this paper. Molecular dynamics (MD) provides a useful way to study material behavior at nanoscale. Complex molecular systems have been successfully studied using MD [17, 18]. The ability of molecular dynamics for simulating fracture in large scale atomic systems has also been successfully demonstrated [19]. The use of J-integral [20] as a fracture criterion can be found extensively in literature [21, 22]. There have been attempts to extend the application of the J-integral to nanostructured materials [23], given the need for a suitable metric to quantify debonding along material interfaces at the nanoscale (e.g. grain boundary decohesion, dislocation, debonding between CNT and polymer matrix, etc.). At finite temperatures, the proper stress potential depends on the process or ensemble. Consequently, the Helmholtz free energy is the proper potential for computing stress at finite temperatures given an isothermal process as it includes the entropic contribution, whereas the internal energy is the appropriate potential for an isentropic process [24]. Because free energy is complex to compute directly since it inherently involves computation of entropy density, it is not surprising that most attempts at estimating atomistic J-integral to date were performed at near zero temperatures [25], where differences between the internal energy and Helmholtz free energy are not significant. A novel MD-based methodology for computing the J-integral in nanostructured materials

through the construction of continuum fields from discrete atomic data through the use of localization functions [26] has been recently developed [23]. These continuum fields were subsequently used to compute contour-integral expression for J that involves gradients of continuum fields, such as, the deformation gradient tensor. There have been other attempts at studying fracture at finite temperature [27, 28] but none of these past attempts have made use of the free energy, except for a recent work [29].

2 ATOMISTIC J-INTEGRAL EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

The objective of this work is to be able to use MD simulations to compute atomistic J-integral, in order to quantify the influence of nanofillers (such as graphene platelets) on phenomenon such as debonding and delamination crack propagation in a polymer composite. The J-integral evaluation scheme discussed below will be subsequently applied to polymeric systems to evaluate fracture metrics, such as toughness and resistance to crack growth (R-curve). In conventional macro-scale fracture mechanics, the total J-integral vector (J_T), defined as the divergence of the Eshelby stress tensor (refer to Eq. (1)), has been used to quantify the crack driving force available from thermo-mechanical loading as well as material inhomogeneities.

$$J_T = \int_{\partial\Omega} \langle \underline{S} \rangle N dA = \int_{\partial\Omega} \langle \langle \Psi \rangle N - \langle \underline{H}^T \underline{P} \rangle N \rangle dA = J_U - J_\eta \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), \underline{S} is the Eshelby stress tensor, Ψ is the free energy density, \underline{H} is the displacement gradient tensor, \underline{P} is the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, N is the outward normal to the surface $\partial\Omega$ along which contour the J-integral is being evaluated, J_U is the contribution to J-integral due to internal energy (U) computed from Eq. (2), and J_η is the entropic contribution computed using Eq. (8). Here it is assumed that ensemble average $\langle * \rangle$ is approximated by the time average of the quantity over a sufficiently long period of time. The critical value of scalar component J_k at crack initiation is related to the fracture toughness of the material, where the subscript k denotes Cartesian components of the J vector (k=1, 2, 3) in three-dimensions and these components are related to, but are not the same as the three primary fracture modes.

Specifically, $J_1 = J^I + J^{II} + J^{III}$ and $J_2 = -2\sqrt{(J^I J^{II})}$, where subscripts imply Cartesian components of the J-vector, and the superscripts imply standard fracture modes [30]. In the absence of Mode III, i.e., for in-plane deformation, the above equations can be solved to obtain the fracture modes, $J^I = \frac{J_1 \pm \sqrt{J_1^2 - J_2^2}}{2}$, and $J^{II} = J_1 - J^I$. Therefore, the Cartesian components of the J-integral can be used as a suitable metric for estimating the crack driving force as well as the fracture toughness of a material as the crack begins to initiate, for Mode I, Mode II and for mixed mode fracture processes undergoing proportional loading. However, for the conventional macroscale definition of the J-integral to be valid at the nanoscale in terms of the continuum stress and displacement fields (and their spatial derivatives) requires the construction of local continuum fields from discrete atomistic data, and using these data in the conventional contour integral expression for J, as given by Eq. (1) [23,29]. One such methodology was proposed by Hardy [26], that allows for the local averaging necessary to obtain the definition of free energy, deformation gradient, and Piola-Kirchhoff stress as fields (and divergence of fields) and not just as total system averages. The formulae we used for evaluating each term in Eq. (1) from our MD simulations are given below.

$$J_U = \int_{\partial\Omega} \langle \langle U \rangle N - \langle \underline{H}^T \underline{P} \rangle N \rangle dA \quad (2)$$

$$U(\mathbf{X}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{\alpha=1}^M N_I(\mathbf{X}) \zeta_{I\alpha} (\mathbf{X}^\alpha - \mathbf{X}_I) \phi^\alpha(t) - U_R(\mathbf{X}) \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{H}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^K \sum_{\alpha=1}^M \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} N_I(\mathbf{X}) \zeta_{I\alpha}(\mathbf{X}^\alpha - \mathbf{X}_I) \mathbf{u}^\alpha(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\underline{P}(\mathbf{X}, t) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^M \sum_{\beta \neq \alpha}^M \mathbf{f}^{\alpha\beta} \otimes \mathbf{X}^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{B}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{X}) \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (3), ϕ^α is atomistic potential of atom α , $\phi_{\mathbf{X}}^\alpha$ is the reference potential energy density of atom α at 0K, ζ is the Hardy localization function, M is the number of atoms in the localization box, $U_R(\mathbf{X})$ is a constant, and $N_I(\mathbf{X})$ are interpolation functions, with $I=1, K$, where K is the total number of nodes. In Eq. (4), $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t)$ is the displacement vector. In Eq. (5), $\mathbf{f}^{\alpha\beta}$ is the vector representing the force between atoms α and β , $\mathbf{X}^{\alpha\beta}$ is the vector representing the difference in their positions, and $\mathbf{B}^{\alpha\beta}$ is the bond function defined by Hardy [26]. A detailed description for evaluation of each term required to calculate atomistic J-integral can be found elsewhere [31]. From statistical mechanics, the Helmholtz free energy density is given by [29],

$$\Psi = U - T\eta = -\frac{k_B T}{V} \text{Log } Z \quad (6)$$

where U is the internal energy density, T is the temperature, η is the entropy density, V is the volume of the ensemble, k_B is Boltzmann's constant and Z is the partition function of the atoms occupying the region. Note that the general definition of free energy density Ψ includes the entropy term and therefore is valid for finite temperature applications of the atomistic J-integral. As mentioned earlier, the conventional definition of J-integral under isothermal condition does not take into account the entropic contribution to the free energy, and consequently, may lead to significant over-estimation of the J-integral at the atomistic level at elevated temperature. As alluded to in Eq. (1), total J-integral at a finite temperature is given by

$$J_T = J_U - J_\eta \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (7), J_U is the value of J-integral without considering entropic contribution and is given by Eq. (2). J_η is the entropic contribution which becomes significant at sufficiently high temperatures due to thermal excitation of the atoms. This entropic contribution to the J-integral can be quantified for a defect free crystalline material using the local harmonic (LH) approximation and is given by [29],

$$J_\eta = \int_{\partial\Omega} \left\langle \frac{k_B T}{V_\alpha} \log \left(\left(\frac{\hbar}{k_B T} \right)^3 \sqrt{\det D_{LH}} \right) \right\rangle N dA \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8), k_B is Boltzmann's constant, \hbar is Planck's constant, V_α is volume of the atom, T is the absolute temperature, and D_{LH} is the dynamical matrix based on the LH approximation of atoms vibrating within a defect-free crystal lattice. The LH approximation is essentially an Einstein model of the vibrational frequencies and has been used extensively in MD-continuum coupling. From statistical mechanics, the dynamical matrix required for quantifying entropic contribution to J-integral is given by [29],

$$\mathbf{D}_{LH} = \frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \mathbf{u}_0^2} = \frac{1}{m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{u}_0} \sum_{\beta \neq 0} \phi(\mathbf{r}_{\beta 0}) \frac{\mathbf{r}_{\beta 0}}{r_{\beta 0}} \quad (9)$$

where, $\Phi = \frac{1}{2V} \sum_{\alpha} \sum_{\beta \neq 0} \phi(\mathbf{r}_{\alpha\beta})$, m is the atomic mass, $\phi(\mathbf{r})$ is the pairwise potential, V is the volume,

$\mathbf{r}_{\beta 0}$ is the position vector of the atom, which results in

$$D_{LH} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{\beta \neq 0} (\phi''(r_{\beta 0}) \frac{\overline{r_{\beta 0}}}{r_{\beta 0}} \otimes \frac{\overline{r_{\beta 0}}}{r_{\beta 0}} + \phi'(r_{\beta 0}) \frac{1}{r_{\beta 0}} [\mathbf{I} - \frac{\overline{r_{\beta 0}}}{r_{\beta 0}} \otimes \frac{\overline{r_{\beta 0}}}{r_{\beta 0}}]) \quad (10)$$

where, \mathbf{I} is identity tensor. Using data from MD simulations in Eq. (10), the dynamical matrix can be evaluated which can then be used to compute the entropic contribution to J-integral using Eq. (8). In this work, m is the atomic mass of carbon (12 grams/mole), V is the volume of the localization box (approximately 2400 \AA^3). Numerical integration through Gaussian quadrature was employed to evaluate atomistic J-integral using the equations given in previous section. The discrete atomistic values of potentials and displacement gradients obtained from MD simulations were converted into field quantities using the finite element interpolation functions for a nine node element (i.e., set $K=9$ in Eq. (3) and (4)) [31].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Atomistic J-integral calculation using graphene sheet at 0 K

In order to verify the atomistic J-integral computation methodology, a single nanographene platelet with a center-crack was modeled using MD (LAMMPS software) and was subjected to a far field uniaxial stress in the Y-direction (pure Mode I loading). The atomistic J-integral was computed on concentric contours as shown in Figure 2. In this example, the graphene platelet was modeled using harmonic style for bonds and angles, and OPLS style for dihedrals. The graphene platelet, measuring $10.5 \text{ nm} \times 10 \text{ nm} \times 0.34 \text{ nm}$, was made up of 4420 carbon atoms. The initial length of the pre-existing (starter) crack was 2.2 nm in the graphene platelet as shown in Figure 2. The coarse time-step for the problem (Δt) was set equal to 0.1 femtoseconds and the applied strain rate was $2 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$. In order to establish proof-of-concept for atomistic J-integral computation, the initial MD simulations were carried out at temperature $T = 0 \text{ K}$, that is, when there is no entropic contribution to the free energy in accordance with Eq. (6). Pressure barostatting was not used in these simulations. A convergence study was conducted on the effect of localization box size on the computed values of stress in the graphene sheet away from the crack tip. The computed value of stress becomes box-size independent for box sizes greater than 2 nm ($\sim 20 \text{ \AA}$). The atomistic J-integral results are shown as a function of applied Mode I stress intensity factor (K_I) in Figure 3 for a graphene platelet and compared with linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) predictions. The plot shows computed values for the three paths around the crack for a localization box-size of 27 \AA . The figure shows that the quadratic dependence of the atomistic J-integral on Mode I stress intensity factor (K_I) is in good agreement with plane-stress LEFM predictions for pure Mode I loading, i.e., $J_I = K_I^2 / (E / (1 - \nu^2))$, where E is the Young's modulus ($E = 0.85 \text{ TPa}$) and ν is the Poisson's ratio ($\nu = 0.2$) of nanographene at 0 K obtained from MD simulations. The figure also verifies that J is identically zero in the absence of a singularity within the integration contour, as depicted by the horizontal line with solid circles. More importantly, it is clear from Figure 3 that the calculated value of J_I is reasonably path-independent for the graphene platelet, even at the nanoscale. This result facilitates the use of calculating J_k at finite temperatures using a cohesive-contour technique, which will be discussed later.

Figure 2. Graphene sheet with nanoscale crack and contours for J-integral computation

Figure 3. Atomistic J_I vs. K_I for a graphene platelet at 0 K using OPLS compared with LEFM (27 Å localization box size)

3.2 Atomistic J-integral calculation using graphene sheet at 300 K

The J-integral evaluation methodology that was verified for a graphene platelet at 0 K was subsequently used for the finite temperature case at 300 K for the same center-cracked platelet. As discussed earlier, entropic contribution (due to $T\eta$ term in Eq. (6)) could have a significant effect on the computed J-integral value, because that portion of the free energy goes into thermal expansion and, therefore, is not available for crack growth.

Figure 4. J-integral contour for the cohesive-contour based technique

As defined in Eq. (7), total atomistic J-integral at finite temperature (J_T) is given by $J_T = J_U - J_\eta$, where J_U is the contribution to J-integral due to internal energy (U) computed from the scheme discussed in Eq. (2), and J_η is the entropic contribution (Eq. (8)). This methodology is only applicable to a defect-free crystalline structure and hence cannot be applied to amorphous polymers [29]. However, the path independence of J-integral facilitates the use of a cohesive-contour based technique to compute J-integral [32]. For the purpose of benchmark feasibility study, a J-integral contour in the shape of a narrow strip encompassing the thin cohesive-contour ahead of the crack tip is constructed in the nanographene platelet as illustrated in Figure 4. Because of the way the contour is designed, it can be shown that by making the contour width (h) sufficiently small, the Helmholtz free energy term can be ignored from the J-integral equation for Mode I as well as for mixed mode loadings. To gain better insight into this approach, let us consider the scalar (indicial) form of the expression for total J-integral,

$$(J_T)_k = \int_{\Gamma} \langle \Psi \delta_{kj} - P_{ij} H_{ik} \rangle N_j d\Gamma \quad (11)$$

where, Ψ is the Helmholtz free energy density, δ_{kj} is the Kronecker delta, and repeated indices imply summation. If we set $k=1$ to obtain $(J_T)_1$, and $j=2$ to define the normal N_2 along the narrow cohesive-contour in Figure 4, the first term on the RHS of Eqn. (11) vanishes because $\delta_{12} = 0$ by definition. Therefore, the only terms that need to be evaluated along the narrow cohesive-contour are the Cartesian components of the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor (P_{i2}), and components of the displacement gradient tensor (H_{i1}), using Eqns. (5) and (4) respectively, giving

$$(J_T)_1 = \int_{\Gamma} \langle -P_{i2} H_{i1} \rangle N_2 d\Gamma \quad (12)$$

This approach is especially useful for thermoset polymers since the LH approximation based approach in Eqn. (8) cannot be used for quantifying entropic contribution for amorphous (disordered) thermoset polymers. For preliminary verification of this novel approach, atomistic J-integral was computed for a center-cracked graphene platelet at a temperature of 300 K. The graphene platelet used is the same as the one used for 0 K computations as shown in Figure 2. The system was elevated to 300 K and was allowed to equilibrate at 300 K and at a pressure of zero atmospheres using NPT fix in LAMMPS. Poisson's effect was considered in this simulation and a value of 0.22 was used for the Poisson's ratio, which is in good agreement with literature [33]. The graphene platelet was stretched under Mode I tension, as was the case for 0 K, and the resulting MD data was used to compute atomistic J-integral. Figure 5 shows the atomistic J-integral comparison using Eqns. (8) and (12), compared with LEFM prediction. J_U is the portion of the atomistic J-integral which includes only internal energy contribution, (that is, without entropic contribution) averaged over 5 concentric paths. As expected, it shows good agreement with strain-energy based LEFM results. J_T is the total computed J-integral including both energetic and entropic contributions (again, averaged over 5 paths) and it is evident that it is significantly (~50%) lower than LEFM predictions, in accordance with Eq. (7). Figure 5 also shows J_{cohesive} computed using the novel cohesive-contour technique described in Eq. (12), and it is in good agreement with J_T . This is an important benchmark result, as it potentially

enables the use of cohesive-contour based technique for computing J-integral at the nanoscale for the case of amorphous polymers, where direct computation of entropic contribution using the LH approximation approach is not feasible.

Figure 5. Atomistic J_I vs. K_I for a graphene platelet at 300 K with OPLS potential and 27 Å localization box size

3.3 Atomistic J-integral calculation using graphene sheet with ReaxFF

While the OPLS force field works well for evaluating mechanical properties, it cannot simulate the phenomena such as bond forming and breakage. In order to better understand the fracture behavior of the material, it is important to be able to simulate crack initiation and propagation. For that purpose, a new force field, ReaxFF, was necessary. ReaxFF is a bond order based force field which allows for continuous bond formation/breaking [34]. Bonded interactions are generated on-the-fly, based on distance-dependent bond order functions. As in the case of OPLS, ReaxFF potential is given by a summation of potentials from various characteristics of a chemical system. The general equation for a ReaxFF potential is given in equation (13).

$$E_{total} = E_{bond} + E_{overcoordination} + E_{undercoordination} + E_{valence} + E_{torsion} + E_{conjugation} + E_{Coulomb} + E_{non-bonded} \quad (13)$$

Each energy term in Eq. (13) is a function of bond order, which is a characteristic parameter of ReaxFF and which in turn, is a function of interatomic distance. The bond order decreases exponentially as the bond length increases. Each energy term contributes to interatomic force which is required for J-integral evaluation. Force contributions are computed by taking derivatives of potential terms and are used for calculating J-integral. As a benchmark case study, MD simulations were carried out on a center-cracked nano-graphene sheet, this time using ReaxFF force field using the potential parameters from literature [35]. The nano-graphene sheet consists of 4398 atoms and is similar in dimensions to the one used in OPLS simulations i.e. 105 Å x 100 Å. An initial central crack of approximately 20 Å was generated by deleting the atoms at the center of the graphene sheet. All the finite temperature simulations were done using NPT fix in order to fully account for Poisson's effect. A timestep of 0.1 femtosecond and a strain rate of 3×10^{11} /second were used for the simulations. A total

tensile strain of approximately 25% was applied on the MD simulation box in the direction perpendicular to the crack to simulate mode I loading. The ReaxFF force field was able to successfully simulate the initiation and propagation of the center crack in the nano-graphene sheet, as depicted in Figure 6. For preliminary benchmarking, atomistic J-integral was evaluated at 0.1 K and 300 K. Based on the results obtained for harmonic OPLS simulations for nanographene, it was established that for a computation box size above 20 Å, the J-integral computations are fairly independent of localization box size. Hence a box size of 27 Å was selected for consistency between OPLS and ReaxFF computations.

Figure 6. Center-cracked graphene at the beginning and end of the simulation using ReaxFF

Figure 7 shows the comparison of atomistic J-integral values computed at 0.1 K using different methods compared to the values from linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) for a localization box size of 27 Å (for one contour). Figure 8 shows the comparison of atomistic J-integral values computed at 300 K using different methods compared to the values from linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) for a localization box size of 27 Å (averaged over 3 contours). In these plots, J_U is the portion of the atomistic J-integral which includes only internal energy contribution, (that is, without entropic contribution), and it shows good agreement with purely strain-energy based LEFM results. J_T is the total computed J-integral including both energetic and entropic contributions, calculated using the partition function approach [23, 29]. J_{Cohesive} is the J-integral value computed using the narrow cohesive contour approach described by Eqn. (12). There is good agreement between LEFM, the energetic J-integral (J_U), and the total J-integral (J_T) at 0.1 K as depicted in Fig. (7), because at 0.1 K the entropic contribution is insignificant as described by Eqn. (6). However, using the classical definition of J (i.e., $J_T=J_U$) does not account for the entropic contribution that becomes significant at higher temperatures (e.g., 300 K), as underscored by the difference between the total J-integral (J_T) and the energetic J-integral (J_U) in Figure 8.

Figure 7. J-interintegral computation for graphene as a function of K_I using ReaxFF at 0.1 K; also shown is change in bond-order with loading (27Å localization box size)

Figure 8. J-interintegral computation in graphene as a function of K_I using ReaxFF at 300K; also shown is change in bond-order with loading (27Å localization box size)

As the temperature increases, the entropic contribution becomes more significant leading to greater than 50% error in the predicted value of total J (J_T), as illustrated in Figure 8. The classical J-interintegral evaluation scheme cannot account for this discrepancy, but the partition function method (J_T) and the cohesive-contour based approach (J_{Cohesive}) are able to account for entropic contribution and are in good agreement with each other as can be seen from Figure 8. The y-axis on the right hand side of the plots also depicts the variation in bond order between the atoms just ahead of the crack tip. It can be observed that as the sheet is stretched in tension, the atomic bond gets stretched, and accordingly

the bond order decreases as a function of loading (K_I). When the bond order becomes zero the bond breaks, providing a critical value of J_T (J_{Ic}) at crack initiation. Interestingly, as shown in Fig. 8, the slopes of the J_T and $J_{Cohesive}$ curves change as the bond order goes to zero, and this critical value ($J_{Ic} = \sim 16 \text{ J/m}^2$) agrees reasonably well with its value published in the literature [36] ($J_{Ic} = 12 \text{ J/m}^2$) for nanographene at 300 K. The oscillations in the bond order value at 300 K are possibly because of thermal excitation of atoms at elevated temperature. The results indicate that the event of bond breakage corresponds fairly well with when the value of computed J-integral deviates from LEFM predictions. This could be considered as the point of crack initiation and could directly be related to the fracture toughness of the material system in a predictive sense.

3.4 Atomistic J-integral calculation for EPON 862 with ReaxFF

The atomistic J-integral computation methodology was successfully verified for a nanographene platelet as discussed earlier. Since it is now established that ReaxFF is more effective in determining crack initiation compared to OPLS, all the MD simulations of the polymer were conducted using ReaxFF potential. A ReaxFF based EPON 862 model with around 4200 atoms ($35 \text{ \AA} \times 35 \text{ \AA} \times 35 \text{ \AA}$) and 85% crosslinking was provided by Dr. Gregory Odegard's research group at Michigan Technological University. The ReaxFF parameters used for this model are available in literature [37]. The initial 4000 atoms system was found to be too small for simulating crack propagation and computing J-integral. Hence, a larger system was constructed by replicating the original system. The new EPON model consists of 16806 atoms with dimensions of $70 \text{ \AA} \times 35 \text{ \AA} \times 70 \text{ \AA}$. Before introducing a crack, the system was subjected to tension and the stress strain response was found to be in agreement with literature [38].

In LAMMPS, regions of specified shape and dimensions can be created. Using that functionality, four "prism" regions were created in the model so that the intersection of those four regions formed a region shaped like a sharp crack. By deleting the atoms present in the intersecting region, a central crack of 26 \AA length was introduced in the epoxy model and was subjected to mode I tension. The simulations were conducted using NVT ensemble with a timestep of 0.005 femtoseconds. A total strain of 50% was gradually applied to the epoxy polymer block. Figure 9 shows the neat EPON 862 model at the beginning and end of the simulation. Crack propagation can be observed clearly in the figure. Similar to nanographene computations, influence of localization box size on the computed values was studied and is presented in Figure 10. From the figure, it is evident that though there is some inconsistency for smaller box sizes, the computed stress values were fairly independent of the localization box size for box size above 25 \AA . Hence, a 27 \AA box size was selected for J-integral computation in order to be consistent with the results obtained for the nanographene model. EPON 862 with nanographene reinforcements ahead of the crack tip and perpendicular to the crack plane was modeled for comparison with the baseline case. A nanographene weight fraction of 3.25% was selected in order to be able to compare numerical results with experiments conducted earlier with a similar weight fraction of nanographene reinforcement. Figure 11 depicts the reinforced EPON 862 model at the beginning and end of the MD simulation, clearly showing the nanographene platelets perpendicular to the crack plane. All the simulation parameters are maintained the same as for the neat EPON simulations. Comparing Figure 11 and Figure 9, it is evident that the crack does not propagate in case of nanographene reinforced EPON model due to the presence of the nanographene platelet perpendicular to the crack plane. Further, there is significant warping of the nanographene platelets indicating energy absorption. The reinforcing effect of nanographene can hence be visualized. Work is underway to quantify this effect and to compare the results with actual experimental data.

Figure 9. Center-cracked neat EPON 862 at the beginning and end of the simulation using ReaxFF

Figure 10. Effect of localization box size on the computed values of stress

Figure 11 . Center-cracked EPON 862 with 3.25 wt% nanographene reinforcement at the beginning and end of the simulation using ReaxFF

4 FUTURE WORK

Unlike the OPLS potential, ReaxFF was able to successfully simulate bond breakage and correlate the breakage to crack initiation in a nano-graphene sheet. The results obtained from J-integral computation using MD show good correlation between bond breakage and the onset of deviation from LEFM in the computed J-integral for nanographene sheet at 300 K. As mentioned earlier, the local harmonic (LH) approximation is not valid for an amorphous (disordered) crosslinked polymer network and an alternate approach using a cohesive contour-based technique is required. Work is currently underway to compute J-integral for nanographene modified EPON 862 at 0.1 K and 300 K using the cohesive-contour based procedure developed and benchmarked in this work. MD simulations of EPON 862 models with and without nanographene reinforcements were successfully performed and they qualitatively indicate that the crack does not propagate in the case of nanographene reinforced EPON model due to the presence of the nanographene platelet perpendicular to the crack plane. Work is underway to quantify this effect and to compare the results with actual experimental data. In order to account for the high strain-rates encountered in MD simulations, scaling laws will need to be developed to correlate fracture toughness predicted by the MD simulations to the toughness data obtained from compact tension fracture experiments.

5 CONCLUSION

The feasibility of computing the dynamic atomistic J-integral over the molecular dynamics (MD) domain at finite temperature was evaluated for a graphene nanoplatelet and the values were compared with results from linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) for isothermal crack initiation at 0 K and at 300 K. Atomistic J-integral computations were also performed using ReaxFF force field in order to simulate bond breakage during crack propagation. Good agreement is observed between the atomistic J and the LEFM results at 0 K, with predictable discrepancies at 300 K due to entropic effects. It is envisioned that a better understanding of the strength enhancement mechanisms at the nanoscale will lead to optimization of materials processing variables at the macroscale, which in turn will lead to the manufacture of nanocomposites more efficiently and at lower cost. The work presented in this paper will help in evaluating properties such as work of separation at nanoscale and incorporate them at higher length scales using multi-scale modeling methods.

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